

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN BIOLOGY STUDENTS' PERCEPTION ON SCHOOL ENVIRONMENTAL VARIABLES AND ACHIEVEMENT IN SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL IN YOBE STATE, NIGERIA

Suleiman, Haruna¹, Aminu, Ahmed Chiroma², Ahmed, Aishatu Musa³, and Ismaila, Amara Gambo⁴

^{1, 2, & 3}Department of Environmental and Life Sciences Education, Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola Adamawa State, Nigeria.

⁴Department of Integrated Science, Federal College of Education, Yola, Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Corresponding Author: aamohammed@mau.edu.ng

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between students' perception on school environmental variables and achievement in senior secondary school biology in Yobe State, Nigeria. Two research questions and two research hypotheses were formulated and tested at a 0.05 level of significance the study. Correlational survey design was adopted for the study. The population for the study comprised 38,230 SSS II students offering biology. Three hundred and seventy (370) SSS II students who were randomly selected from 10 secondary schools as the sample. The instruments used were School Environmental Variables Questionnaire (SEVQ) and Proforma (BRP). Data was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The research questions were answered using descriptive statistic of mean and standard deviation while hypotheses were tested using Spearman's Rank-Order correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that there is no significant relationship in academic achievement between rural and urban students in Yobe State, over urban students performing better ($r = 0.102$, $p = 0.842$). Additionally, the study found that there is no significant relationship between class size and students' achievements in biology in Yobe State ($r = 0.066$, $p = 0.202$). Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that, state government should boost schools with adequate facilities to create a conducive learning environment. Yobe State government should build more classrooms in schools to reduce overcrowding.

Keywords: School Environmental Variables, Students' Perception, Class Size, Biology Students, Achievement

INTRODUCTION

Science education plays a crucial role in building a scientifically informed society equipped to tackle modern global issues such as environmental sustainability, public health emergencies, and rapid technological progress. It encourages critical thinking, fosters inquiry-based learning, and enables learners to apply scientific concepts to everyday life. When effectively delivered, science education not only improves student performance but also cultivates essential skills for innovation and effective problem-solving (Holbrook & Rannikmae, 2018; Bybee, 2017).

Secondary school science education plays a critical role in shaping students' foundational knowledge and guiding their future pursuits in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) fields (Adewale & Ibukun, 2016). In Nigeria, the Federal Government (FGN, 2014) characterizes science education as an integrated field that includes key

scientific disciplines like Biology, Physics, and Chemistry subjects deemed vital for entry into science-based programs at the tertiary education level.

Biology, as a natural science, focuses on exploring life and living organisms by examining their structural makeup, biochemical functions, molecular relationships, physiological processes, life cycles, and evolutionary trajectories (Mohammed & Joda, 2017). It provides essential insight into the origins and persistence of life on Earth. Through its examination of the wide range of living species, biology enhances our understanding of the complexity of organisms including humans, animals, and plants. Additionally, it promotes an awareness of the delicate interconnections between humans and their natural environment, encouraging friendly ecosystems among organisms. As such, biology forms the groundwork for investigating life's various dimensions and is central to efforts aimed at conserving biological diversity.

Despite the pivotal role of biology in scientific education, students' performance in the Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Biology in Yobe State has shown considerable inconsistency in recent years. Between 2018 and 2022, the percentage of candidates who scored below a C6 stood at 36.48%, 45.31%, 55.05%, 37.35%, and 47.71%, respectively. This persistent fluctuation in achievement may be attributed to a range of interrelated factors influencing academic performance, including the quality of instruction, student-related characteristics, and the broader school environment. Notably, teacher-related components such as subject matter expertise, teaching strategies, and classroom management skills play a pivotal role in enhancing students' grasp of biological concepts (Agu & Samuel, 2019; Nwagbo & Uzodimma, 2017). Student-related variables such as motivation, prior knowledge, and study habits play a significant role in shaping academic performance in biology (Owolabi & Adedeji, 2018).

Furthermore, aspects of the school environment such as the presence of well-equipped laboratories, student-teacher ratios, and the availability of teaching materials have been identified as key factors that can either support or hinder students' academic achievement (Ahmed, 2016; Adekunle & Adebayo, 2021). Additional contextual elements, including the quality of physical infrastructure, the school's geographical setting, and the sufficiency of instructional resources, also play a significant role in shaping the effectiveness of biology teaching and the level of student participation.

A school's geographical location plays a significant role in shaping students' academic performance. Studies have shown that institutions located in economically privileged areas such as urban areas often enjoy better facilities, a higher number of professionally trained teachers, and more abundant educational resources compared to those in less developed or rural settings. Urban schools, in particular, tend to provide enriched learning experiences through diverse extracurricular activities and access to advanced technological tools, which can enhance academic outcomes (Zubairu & Ali, 2019). In contrast, schools in rural communities frequently face challenges such as insufficient funding, poor transportation infrastructure, and limited availability of up-to-date teaching materials all of which can negatively impact student achievement (Okoye, 2020). Yusuf (2018) noted that students who are required to travel long distances to school are more likely to experience inconsistent attendance, which may negatively impact their academic achievement. Additionally, the broader social setting of a school including neighborhood safety and local economic conditions also plays a crucial role in shaping student motivation, behavior, and academic success (Adebayo & Ojo, 2021). In regions of Yobe State, for instance, ongoing insecurity linked to Boko Haram insurgency has posed serious obstacles to the education system, particularly in ensuring safe and supportive learning environments. As such, both the geographical location and socio-economic context of schools in Yobe state can either enhance or hinder educational outcomes, highlighting the urgent need for policy measures that address the educational disparities between rural and urban areas (Johnson & Alade, 2022).

Class size continues to be a focal point in educational debates, with extensive research demonstrating a strong link between smaller class sizes and improved student performance. Evidence suggests that reducing the number of students per classroom enables more greater teacher-student interaction, individualized instruction and more efficient classroom control and management all of which are key attributors to academic achievement (Finn et al., 2017; Blatchford et al., 2016). In more compact classroom environments, educators can more effectively tailor their teaching methods to address the varied learning needs of students, an approach especially beneficial for those from low-income backgrounds (Biddle & Berliner, 2016). Additionally, Shin and Raudenbush (2018) indicates that early experiences in smaller class settings may lead to academic advantages, such as improved test scores and heightened engagement in learning activities. These insights may significantly impact class size on teaching quality and learning academic achievement. Accordingly, this study aims to explore how school environmental factors influence students' academic achievement in Yobe State, Nigeria.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between biology students' perception on school environmental variables and achievement in senior secondary school in Yobe state, Nigeria. Therefore, specific objective of the study is to

1. Determine the relationship between school location and achievement of senior secondary school Biology Students in Yobe state, Nigeria.
2. Determine the relationship between Biology students' class size perception and achievement in senior secondary school in Yobe state, Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the mean achievement scores of rural and urban senior secondary school biology students in Yobe state, Nigeria?
2. What is the biology students' class size perception of senior secondary school in Yobe state, Nigeria?

HYPOTHESES

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between rural and urban senior secondary school achievement of senior secondary school biology students' in Yobe state, Nigeria.

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between students' class size perception and achievement of senior secondary school Biology in Yobe state, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a correlational survey design. The area of this study was Yobe State, Nigeria. The population for the study comprised all 38,230 Senior Secondary School II (SSS II) students from 211 public secondary schools located across the three (3) educational zones of Yobe state. The sample size was 370 SSS II Biology students from public senior secondary schools in Yobe State selected to participate in the study. The sample was selected using a multi stage sampling techniques. In the first stage the simple random sampling technique was used to select Potiskum education zone from the three zones. In the second stage, purposive sampling technique was employed to select 10 public secondary schools in

Potiskum education zone. In the final stage, a proportionate sampling technique was employed to select each school based on proportion and this gave a total of 370 respondents for the study. Two instruments were used to collect data for the study namely; School Environmental Variables Questionnaire (SEVQ) adapted from Mc Ghee, Lowell and Lemire (2007), and Biology Results Proforma (BRP) for student’s academic performance in Biology respectively. The SEVQ was face and construct validated by three experts from the Department of Environmental and Life Sciences Education, Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola. To determine the reliability of instruments, a trial test was conducted involving 35 senior secondary school II Biology students who were not part of the main sample. Cronbach Alpha method was used to determine the internal consistency of the instruments and reliability co-efficient of SEVQ were obtained as 0.81 for school location and 0.83 for class size. The instruments were administered by research assistance and retrieved same after completion and students’ academic score were retrieved from the examination officers. The Date were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistic (mean and standard deviation), to answer research questions while hypotheses were tested using Spearman’s rank order correlation at 0.05 level of significance. If the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypotheses will be rejected. However, if the P -value is greater than 0.05 level of significance, do not reject the null hypotheses.

RESULTS

Research Question One: What is the mean achievement of rural and urban senior secondary school students offering biology in Yobe state, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean Achievement of Senior Secondary School Biology Students based on school location in Yobe state, Nigeria

School location	N	Mean	Std Deviation	Mean diff.
Urban	222	53.93	12.430	
Rural	148	49.92	12.365	4.010

The descriptive statistics in table 1 indicates that 370 students responded to the items instrument assessing school location. The table reveal that students in urban had a mean achievement score of 53.93 with standard deviation of 12.43 while students in rural had a mean achievement score of 49.92 with standard deviation of 12.35. The mean difference of 4.010 in favor urban school location than rural areas in Yobe State.

Research Question Two: What is the perception of senior secondary school Biology students on class size in Yobe state, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean response on the perception of senior secondary school biology students on class size in Yobe state, Nigeria

S/N	Perceptions on Class size	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
1	How would you rate your satisfaction with the current class size in term of its impact on your learning experience	3.31	1.576	Disagree
2	How very often do you feel that a larger class size hinders your ability to actively participate in class discussion	3.44	1.244	Disagree
3	To what level do you believe that a smaller class size would positively influence your academic performance	3.47	1.467	Disagree
4	How do you feel approaching your teacher for additional support in a larger class setting	2.90	1.268	Disagree
5	Rate the level of distraction you experience in larger classes compare to smaller classes during lesson.	3.33	1.420	Disagree
6	To what level do you think a smaller class size would enhance teacher-students interaction	3.43	1.346	Disagree
7	How do you find it challenging to focus an academic task due to the size of your current class	3.05	1.443	Disagree
8	To what level your perception of the relationship between class size and your overall achievements	3.31	1.130	Disagree
9	To what level do you think a smaller class size would contribute to a more inclusive learning environment	3.42	1.258	Disagree
10	Rate your confidence level in understanding course content in larger class size versus smaller class size.	2.88	1.209	Disagree
Grand Mean		3.42		Disagree

Key: SA = Strongly Agree, D = Disagree,

Table 2 indicates that 370 students responded to 10 items on the class size among senior secondary school Biology students in Yobe state. Items 1-10 indicated disagree with a grand mean of 3.42. This show that the perception of senior secondary school Biology students on class size in Yobe state, Nigeria disagree with high students’ achievements in both school location be it rural or urban areas in Yobe State.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between school location and students’ achievement in senior secondary school biology students in Yobe state, Nigeria.

Table 3: Result of Spearman’s Rank-order correlation of school location and students’ achievement in senior secondary school biology students in Yobe state, Nigeria

	n	Mean	Mean diff.	Df	r	P level	Remark
Urban	370	53.93					
			4.010	369	0.102	0.842	No significant relationship
Rural	370	49.92					

Table 3 shows that school location had no significant relationship on students' academic achievements in biology among senior secondary school in Yobe State ($r = 0.102, p > 0.05$). This indicates the relationship between school location and achievement in biology is statistically not significantly. This implies that school location and students' achievements does not have significant relationship in biology in senior secondary school in Yobe state

H₀: There is no significant relationship between class size and students' achievement in senior secondary school biology students in Yobe state, Nigeria.

Table 4: Result of Spearman's Rank-order correlation of class size and students' achievements in senior secondary school biology students in Yobe state, Nigeria

	n	Mean	Mean diff.	Df	r	P level	Remark
Class size	370	47.02					
			2.61	369	0.066	0.202	No significant relationship
Academic achievement	370	44.31					

The result in table 4 reveals a significant weak positive relationship between class size and students' achievements in biology senior secondary school in Yobe state ($r = 0.066, p > 0.05$). This indicates that the relationship between class size and students' achievement in biology is statistically not significant. This implies that class size does not significantly affect students' achievements in biology in senior secondary schools in Yobe State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

The study revealed that the school location had no significant relationship on students' academic achievements in biology among senior secondary school in Yobe State. This finding agrees with Awodun and Oyeniyi (2018) found that there was no statistically significant difference in the academic achievement mean scores of male and female students in the urban school areas. On the contrary Umar and Samuel (2018) revealed that students in urban schools had better achievement than those at rural settings. Agbaje and Awodun (2014) revealed that there was statistically significant difference in the achievement mean scores of students in rural and urban school located areas. Babawale (2019) revealed that significant difference existed in academic performance of students in Economics on the ground of school location, but in favor of urban location students. This is because the urban students may have access to educational resources, teacher quality, modern facilities better than urban schools.

The finding also shows that there is no significant relationship between class size and students' achievement in biology in Yobe state. This finding agrees with Owioye (2011) who found no significant difference in the academic achievement of students in small and large classes from urban schools. In contrast, Mustapha, Kachallah and Abulfathi (2021) revealed a strong correlation between class size and students' academic performance in the English Language. Similarly, Akoto-Baako and Kissi-Abrokwah, (2021) reported that large class correlate with psychological class environment and the results shows that there is a statistically significant relationship between the variables. Furthermore, the study showed that students perform well in smaller class size and good psychological classroom environment. In the same vein, Obiakor (2020)

concludes that large class size contributes to poor academic performance, it results to poor teaching methods, instructional materials are not used properly in a large class size because, it is very hard for the teacher to show the students the instructional material especially those at the back.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that school location did not have a statistically significant impact on students' achievement in biology at the senior secondary level in Yobe State, Nigeria. However, it was observed that students in urban schools generally achieved higher academic results compared to their counterparts in rural areas an outcome primarily linked to disparities in infrastructure and geographic advantages. Class size also showed no statistically significant influence on students' academic achievement in the biology.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Yobe State government should boost schools in urban and rural areas with adequate facilities to create a conducive learning environment.
2. Yobe State government should reduce overcrowding by building more classrooms in schools.

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